

Supplementals

Subjects	ARM		STS/BTS			WBR D1				WBR D2				
	DA		VL		ESL1		VL		ESL1		VL		ESL1	
	Right	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	
Young	1	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO
	2	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	Slow	X	X	X	X
	3	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO
	4	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO
	5	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO
	6	X	X	NO	NO	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO
	7	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	Slow	Slow	NO
	8	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	9	X	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	X	Slow	X	X	X	X
	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	11	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	12	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	Slow	X	X	X	X
	13	X	X	NO	X	X	Fast	NO	X	X	X	X	X	X
	14	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	15	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	16	X	X	X	X	Slow	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	17	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	NO	NO	X	X	X	X
	18	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	Slow	X	X	Slow	Slow
	19	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	20	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Old	1	X	X	X	X	Fast	X	X	X	X	X	Fast	X	X
	2	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	NO	X	Slow	Slow	NO
	5	X	X	X	X	X	NO	Slow	Slow	Slow	NO	X	X	X
	6	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	X	NO	NO	X	X	NO	NO
	7	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	X	X	X	X	X
	8	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	9	X	X	NO	X	X	Fast	NO	X	X	Fast	NO	X	X
	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X
	11	X	NO	NO	X	X	NO	NO	X	X	NO	NO	X	X
	12	X	Slow	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X	X	X	NO	X
	13	X	X	X	X	X	X	NO	X	X	Fast	NO	X	X
	14	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	15	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	16	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	17	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	18	X	X	X	Slow	X	X	NO	X	X	X	X	NO	NO
	19	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Fast	Fast	Fast	Fast
	20	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	21	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	22	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	23	X	X	X	X	X	Slow	Slow	Slow	Slow	X	X	X	X
	24	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Supplementary Table 1. Some of the EMG recordings exhibited aberrant values. This table reports the quality of EMG recordings for the main antigravity muscles in each participant (numbered on the left), and each task, i.e. DA (Deltoid Anterior head) during focal arm movements, and VL (Vastus Lateralis) and ESL1 muscles (Erector Spinae at Lumbar 1 level) during global whole-body movements. “X”: all trials were correct. “Fast”: some of the fast trials, maximum 4/12, have been excluded. “Slow”: some of the slow trials, maximum 2/6, have been excluded. “NO”: too many trials exhibited aberrant values and, therefore, the muscle was not used for the analyses presented in this manuscript. STS/BTS: Seat-to-stand/Back-to-seat. WBR D1: Whole body reaching near target. WBR D2: whole body reaching far target.

Task	Direction	Group	Mean (s) ± SD (s)
ARM	Tonic	Upward	OLD 6,104± 2,8
		YOUNG	3,907± 1,4
	Downward	OLD	6,395± 3,6
		YOUNG	3,544± 1,6
	Fast	Upward	OLD 0,221± 0,08
		YOUNG	0,210± 0,08
Downward	OLD	0,249± 0,10	
	YOUNG	0,213± 0,08	
STS/BTS	Tonic	Upward	OLD 2,144± 0,7
		YOUNG	1,698± 0,5
	Downward	OLD	2,858± 1,0
		YOUNG	2,141± 0,6
	Fast	Upward	OLD 0,357± 0,09
		YOUNG	0,267± 0,05
Downward	OLD	0,396± 0,11	
	YOUNG	0,279± 0,04	
WBR D1	Tonic	Upward	OLD 4,009± 1,2
		YOUNG	3,106± 1,0
	Downward	OLD	3,375± 0,9
		YOUNG	2,739± 0,7
	Fast	Upward	OLD 0,521± 0,11
		YOUNG	0,419± 0,05
Downward	OLD	0,458± 0,07	
	YOUNG	0,389± 0,05	
WBR D2	Tonic	Upward	OLD 4,083± 1,3
		YOUNG	3,276± 0,9
	Downward	OLD	3,594± 1,2
		YOUNG	2,747± 0,8
	Fast	Upward	OLD 0,529± 0,10
		YOUNG	0,445± 0,06
Downward	OLD	0,525± 0,09	
	YOUNG	0,442± 0,05	

Supplementary Table 2. Mean movement durations ± (SD) are presented for each task, movement direction, movement speed and age-group. STS/BTS = Sit To Stand / Back To Sit; WBR D1 = Whole-Body Reaching near target; WBR D2 = Whole-Body reaching far target.

	Effects	F	p-value	Effect size (partial η^2)
A. Movement duration	Type of Tasks effect	433	9,38E-24	0,911
	Age effect	14,5	4,58E-04	0,256
ANCOVA Age x Type of Tasks	Age x Type of Tasks effect	20,0	5,72E-05	0,322
B. Negativity Index	Type of Tasks effect	0,53	4,70E-01	0,013
	Age effect	0,54	4,68E-01	0,013
ANCOVA Age x Whole-body tasks	Age x Type of Tasks effect	5,48	2,44E-02	0,120
C. Negativity Index	Whole-body Tasks effect	0,78	9,30E-01	0,002
	Age effect	4,50	4,00E-02	0,103
ANCOVA Age x Type of Tasks	Age x Whole-body Tasks effect	0,77	4,67E-01	0,019
D. Negativity Duration	Whole-body Tasks effect	0,32	7,20E-01	0,009
	Age effect	21,5	4,54E-05	0,374
ANCOVA Age x Whole-body tasks	Age x Distance effect	2,49	8,99E-02	0,065
E. Negativity Amplitude	Whole-body Tasks effect	0,63	5,37E-01	0,017
	Age effect	1,16	2,80E-01	0,031
ANCOVA Age x Whole-body tasks	Age x Distance effect	0,72	4,89E-01	0,020
F. Negativity Frequency	Whole-body Tasks effect	0,39	6,75E-01	0,011
	Age effect	3,62	6,50E-02	0,091
ANCOVA Age x Whole-body tasks	Age x Distance effect	0,358	7,01E-01	0,010

Supplementary Table 3. Details of the statistical analyses presented in the manuscript for **A.** the movement duration, **B.** the negativity index for whole-body tasks, **C.** the negativity index for the comparison arm and whole-body tasks, **D.** the negativity duration for whole-body tasks, **E.** the negativity amplitude for whole-body tasks, and **F.** the negativity frequency for whole-body tasks. Are gathered in the table the F, the p-value and the effect size (partial η^2).

Supplementary Figure 1. Reproduction of the analyses of Paizis et al. (2008) (panels **A** and **B**) and Casteran et al. (2018) (panels **C** and **D**). Both studies showed age-related differences in motor skills during balance tasks (downward whole-body reaching tasks).

Paizis et al. (2008). We computed the two main criteria used by Paizis et al. (2008): the whole deviation and the downward vertical center of mass (CoM) displacement. The whole deviation was computed using a trapezoidal numerical integration from Matlab [Mat, 2021] to obtain the area between the actual trajectory from the wrist and the straight path between movement start and end. The downward vertical displacement was computed on the CoM using the mathematical seven-segment model of the body detailed in the manuscript between movement start and end and was normalized by the height of the participant. Paizis et al. (2008) only tested one distance. We observe an interaction Age x Distance effect where Paizis et al. (2008), with only one distance, only observe an Age effect. We observe the same Age effect as they did for the vertical CoM displacement, with the younger participants having more displacement than the older ones. The results we found are in direct agreement with those obtained by the authors.

Casteran et al. (2018). We computed the two main criteria used by Casteran et al. (2018): the relative duration to peak vertical velocity of the CoM and the relative duration to crossover point. The relative duration to peak vertical velocity of the CoM was obtained using the mathematical seven-segment model of the body detailed in the manuscript between movement start and end. The crossover point between the anteroposterior and vertical velocities was obtained by decomposing the CoM velocity profile into its Antero-Posterior (Δ AP trajectory) and Vertical (Δ V) components. The point of interest is the moment when the vertical component surpasses the antero-posterior one. Casteran et al. (2018) tested the same two

distances. We observe an Age effect for the relative time to peak vertical velocity, as Casteran et al. (2018) did, suggesting a vertical peak velocity occurring earlier for older participants. We found an Age effect for the crossover point between vertical and antero-posterior components of the CoM velocity, while Casteran et al. (2018) suggested that – but did not directly test – there may exist an interaction effect Age x Distances. The present results do not validate the supposed interaction effect. Distance does not seem to more strongly affect the movements of older adults compared to younger adults.